

Enhancing Swinburne University's Research Data Management Policy

An implementation project for the Institutional
Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Swinburne University

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

Building on the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Policy element, Swinburne University has built a new policy. The policy was drafted based on the published experiences for a variety of international institutes and organisations, assessment of existing policies across the 20 largest Australian universities, and consultation with many university roles. More information can be found within the documentation on Zenodo.

Just as importantly, however, we have developed a suite of supporting materials (collected in DOI:[10.5281/zenodo.6776054](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6776054) summarised in the figure below). The aim is to aid compliance and ensure best practice with minimum cognitive and administrative burden on researchers. In particular the focus has been:

- Keep broadly consistent organisation and messaging around research data management (RDM) relevant information by structuring it around the familiar research life-cycle (planning, gathering, storage, analysis, visualisation, dissemination)
- For researchers, focus on efficiency gains and potential research capability or impact improvements
- For university executive, focus on funder compliance, journal mandates, and institutional risk mitigation

A summary landing webpage on the university's intranet acts as a hub for researchers to find information specific to their needs and links to FAQs, an annotated and illustrated copy of the policy with in-line compliance advice, extensive 'how-to' style guidelines, and the weekly training data clinic series of workshops and panel discussions.

The communications strategy focuses on:

- Summary overview presentations (at each school or department)
 - To leadership: focus on benefits to the institution and compliance requirements
 - To broader researcher community: focus on benefits to individuals, key principles, and where/when to get further information
- More specific in-depth training (university-wide) on particular topics of interest through workshops and panel discussions
- Supporting information disseminated via relevant university newsletters

Figure: Summary of supporting materials.

Resulting Improvements

Swinburne is now on track to implement an RDM policy, which had been a requirement for some time. Importantly, researchers are being ‘set up for success’ with broad ranging support in the form of reading material, presented material, user-friendly document templates and in-person advice. Even the provision of university-wide templates for research data management plans (RDMP) has been valuable, as previously only some schools had an RDMP template, and these were different templates, leading to significantly different practices for data.

It is our hope that these activities have laid the foundation for the intended cultural change around RDM at the university – particularly around open data, drawing on other elements of the Research Data Management for Institutions Framework. This cultural change is a long-term project, so we will run follow-up surveys at several time intervals in the future to measure progress and identify lagging areas.

Next Steps

Swinburne intends the following will continue after the project:

- Continued training
 - University-wide workshops and clinics by topic
 - Tailored consultations for individual research groups or teams
- Surveys to see if practices are being updated
- Implementation of a needed institutional repository to properly support open data practices
- Statistics on uptake of provided platforms (e.g. total volume in cloudstor, and institutional repository)
- Observations and stakeholder on how researcher behaviour changes (or lags)
- Planned intervention points for a just-in-time process, eventually via more integrated systems e.g.:
 - Integrate systems for RDMPs & ethics applications & approved grants & data sharing agreements (DSA)
 - Integrate open data repository & research outputs management system

Project Outputs

Standardised research data management policy templates and supporting materials.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6776054](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6776054)

As summarised in the above figure, the material outputs are:

- Modular research data management policy, broadly organised around the research lifecycle, including summary illustrations and inline compliance advice
- Template documents for RDMPs, DSAs, READMEs, metadata example, offboarding handover
- Communications material, including:
 - Briefing paper proposing the new policy to senior leadership
 - 'Tip- of the week' newsletter items
 - Example tweets
- Training material

- Broad introductory presentation outlining key principles and highlighting potential in-depth topics
- More in-depth presentations on various topics
- Extensive, 'how-to' style practice guidelines document
- FAQ on commonly required information or misunderstood points

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).